

UNDERSTANDING LEARNING MATERIALS IN EDUCATION

Abdullayeva Sarvinoz Xayrullo qizi

Student of Samarkand State Institut of Foreign language

Gmail: sarvinoz6763@gmail.com

Scientific supervisor: **Zubaydova Nilufar Nematullayevna**

Teacher of Samarkand State Institut of Foreign language

Abstract: This article discusses the role of learning materials in the learning process and their impact on effectiveness. The article is aimed at studying the processes of adoption and adaptation of educational materials. It is important to adapt educational materials to the age, characteristics, and learning styles of students. The article also highlights the advantages of providing educational materials in interactive and digital formats.

Keywords: Educational materials, admission process, adaptation, educational effectiveness, age of students, characteristics of students, learning styles, digital format, visual materials, interactive textbooks, graphics, technologies, learning motivation, cultural adaptation, independent study.

INTRODUCTION

Educational materials are the main tool in the educational process. Through these materials, students acquire new knowledge, receive various information and form various skills based on them. The content of educational materials, the form of their presentation and adaptation have a direct impact on the effectiveness of education. That is why the study and analysis of the processes of adoption and adaptation of educational materials is of great theoretical and practical importance.

Main part

The reception of educational materials is understood as the process of students' understanding and assimilation of information obtained from textbooks, manuals, multimedia resources and other educational tools. This process depends on the individual characteristics, level of knowledge and learning styles of students. Each student perceives materials in his own way. While some people read and understand texts, others absorb the material better through visual images or audio information. Therefore, the task of teachers is to develop educational materials in accordance with different styles and present them in different formats.

In order for educational materials to reach students correctly and effectively, they should be adapted to various factors. Age characteristics, individual needs, learning abilities, and learning styles of students play a key role in adapting educational materials. For example, educational materials for school-age students should be presented through colorful pictures, graphics, and interesting images, as they help students to gain attention and absorb information. Educational materials intended for young people should have more in-depth analysis and broader explanations, because students of this age will have the skills of independent study and analysis of materials.

Another important factor affecting the process of learning materials is the level of readiness of students. The fact that students have previously prepared knowledge, skills and experiences is of crucial importance in the process of effective learning of materials. In this process, teachers should prepare materials in accordance with the learning process of students. For example, for elementary school students, information should be simple and understandable, texts should be short and meaningful. In this case, students gradually expand their knowledge. Students' individual learning styles also influence the acceptance of learning materials. For most students, visual presentations, graphs, charts, and tables help to better understand the material. Other learners focus more on texts or audio information. Also, students who prefer kinesthetic learning rely on hands-on activities and experiences. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account different learning styles in the development of educational materials and in the process of their adoption.

The form of their presentation is also of great importance for the effective reception and assimilation of educational materials. Various technologies and digital tools are widely used in modern education. For example, interactive textbooks, videos, simulations and other multimedia tools make the learning process interesting and effective for students. Providing learning materials in digital format is convenient for students as they can review, learn and revise these materials on time.

Adaptation of educational materials means adapting them to the needs and abilities of students. This process helps students overcome the difficulties they face in the process of learning. For example, learning materials can be redesigned based on students' language level, knowledge level, and individual learning needs. In this case, students can use additional resources or aids to master the material. For example, explanatory glossaries or graphics can be added for difficult texts. At the

same time, by simplifying the materials, it is possible to make them understandable and easy to accept.

In addition, in the process of adapting educational materials, their cultural compatibility is also important. Each learner has their own cultural and social context, which influences how they perceive learning materials. Therefore, when developing educational materials, it is necessary to take into account their cultural aspects and adapt them to the cultural skills of students. For example, for students studying in international schools, it is necessary to ensure that educational materials are understandable in different cultural contexts. Such adaptation helps students to better absorb and understand the material.

Another important factor in the process of receiving educational materials is the motivation of students. If students are interested in learning materials and motivated to learn them, they will absorb the materials more effectively. Therefore, it is important to prepare educational materials in an interesting and stimulating way. For example, interactive learning materials, problem-solving tasks, and engaging lessons are effective tools for engaging students.

At the same time, their integration in the educational process is of great importance in the adoption of educational materials. Educational materials should correspond to the goals and objectives of the lesson and actively involve students in the learning process. How learning materials are presented in textbooks and how they are used affects students' motivation to learn. Teachers have a big role in this process, they should use educational materials correctly and effectively in the lesson.

CONCLUSION

In short, the process of receiving and adapting educational materials plays an important role in increasing the efficiency of students' learning. In order to successfully organize this process, teachers must take into account the individual needs, abilities and learning styles of students.

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